

De-ideologising laïcité: a summit we share, paths we fight over

What if agreeing on the goal reopened the debate on the means?

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Abstract. *Public debate on secularism stalls because the word has become a banner: we label, we accuse, we stop listening. A detour through the history and geography of the “wall of separation” shows that one word covers opposite objects. Going back to the purpose of secularism — holding a plural society together — reveals a summit almost everyone shares; our disagreements then bear only on the paths to reach it, and those, in turn, can be discussed. This column opens a series.*

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1. A word turned into a banner

Recently, sharing with a friend the project that has occupied me for years — rethinking secularism, neither to defend nor to attack it, but to understand it —, I saw his face light up with an obvious thought: “Good timing, with the elections coming up.” The remark was kindly, almost encouraging. Yet I replied that my purpose was commanded neither by that calendar nor by that country; that I was after something slower, more lasting and, I hope, of universal reach. He smiled, a little surprised — as if the very idea that one might speak of secularism outside a battle of the moment had something incongruous about it.

It is that surprise that stopped me. For it betrays a reflex so widespread we no longer notice it: the moment one utters the word “laïcité” (secularism), one ties it at once to a balance of power, an election, a camp. As if the word had no existence but a polemical one, as if it were made only to serve a quarrel.

This reflex is not trivial. It is the symptom of a drift we have collectively let happen: we have turned a concept into a banner. A concept is defined, discussed, revised as one understands it better; a banner is brandished, defended, rallied to. The first calls for argument; the second, for belonging. And one does not refute a belonging.

The signs of this drift are everywhere, down to our most ordinary turns of phrase. We say “this is secular”, “that person is secular”, as though it were a characteristic one either has or lacks — a kind of certificate of good civic conduct, granted to some, denied to others. And behind the label a suspicion sets in: whoever is not stamped with it must, by default, belong to the other side — clerical, sectarian, suspect, who knows. We also say, as a set phrase, “that is an attack on

secularism” — sometimes about a public official who meets the representatives of a faith, even as he does so in the interest of the community. In such uses, the word no longer describes anything: it classifies, it accuses, it splits the world in two, when the world itself is not binary. This is how an instrument of concord ends up feeding discord.

2. One word, many worlds

Yet one need only lift one’s eyes from the news, and travel a little, to watch the word come apart in our hands. In France, secularism is rooted in the 1905 law and places neutrality on the side of the State, which neither recognises nor funds any religion. In Quebec, a recent law shifted that neutrality onto the appearance of certain public employees — a conception the France of 1905 would not have recognised as its own. In the United States, the First Amendment raises a “wall of separation” that protects the State, within a society that has nonetheless remained deeply religious, down to its banknotes. In India, the Constitution proclaims itself “secular” not to keep religions at a distance but to recognise them all equally, the State wishing to be equidistant rather than absent. In Turkey, the same principle long designated the exact opposite of a separation: tight control of religion by the State. Five countries, one word, five incompatible objects.

The ambiguity is so old that it affects even the founding image of the genre. That famous “wall of separation” we cite at every turn — we forget that it was first raised, in the seventeenth century, by a dissenting minister, Roger Williams, founder of the colony of Rhode Island. For him, the wall was to protect “the garden of the Church” from the encroachments of “the world”: it was about sheltering faith from power, not the reverse. Only much later would Thomas Jefferson reverse its meaning, making the same wall the rampart of the State against the interference of the Church. One image, two diametrically opposed intentions. And we find this paradoxical legacy again, in France’s 1905 debates, in the mouths of those who argued that separation came not to fight faith but to protect it — by guaranteeing each person freedom of conscience. Secularism, to hear them, was not aimed against believers: it was the condition for them to believe in peace.

What is to be drawn from this apparent disorder? One thing, and it is liberating: if a single word covers realities so diverse, then most of our quarrels bear not on secularism, but on *which* secularism. We think we are clashing over answers, when we are using the same syllables for different questions. So long as this misunderstanding lasts, the debate settles nothing: it merely heats up.

3. Back to the purpose

How, then, to climb out of the rut? The temptation would be to offer, in my turn, a definition — the right one, at last. That would be to add a banner to the banners. I would rather do the opposite: not to say what secularism *is*, but to recall what it is *for*. To climb back, in short, from the quarrel over means to the question of the end. For it is on the purpose, and perhaps on it alone, that agreement becomes possible.

Secularism is not an end in itself; it is a means. A device — legal, social, political — patiently built to solve a problem every plural society eventually meets: how can women and men who do not believe the same things nonetheless hold together? How to make, out of a diversity of convictions, a single body politic — a society that does not tear itself apart, a community habitable by all? Secularism is one of the historical answers to that question; in its modern form, it is bound up with what we call the nation — that political community where one may believe, doubt or not believe without ceasing to belong to the same whole. That summit — holding a divided society together —, who truly contests it? Almost no one. Believers and non-believers, on one side or the other, almost all would subscribe to it. It is visible to all, and that is what makes it precious.

4. Paths, not summits

And it is here that everything turns. If we share the summit, then our disagreements bear not on the destination but on the paths to reach it: should neutrality weigh on the State alone, or also on individuals? How far, at what pace, in which places? These are questions of route, of itinerary. Now an itinerary can be discussed: one can weigh its advantages, its costs, its detours; one can change one's mind, correct course. It is the very opposite of a banner, which one does not discuss but displays. Disagreement over means belongs to the order of the negotiable, the revisable — the decidable. The tragedy of our public debate is that it constantly disguises disagreements over paths as wars over summits: each ends up suspecting the other of not really wanting the same community — whereas, most often, it is the road, and the road alone, that divides them.

Make no mistake: to de-ideologise secularism is not to depoliticise it. The choice of paths remains an eminently political choice, and it belongs to citizens, not to scholars or experts. It is merely to refuse that the word precede the thing, that the banner dispense with thought. It is to put the summit back at the centre — to recall the shared purpose — so as to be able, at last, to debate the routes without putting one another's intentions on trial. It is, to put it in an image, to stop confusing the map with the territory: we think we are fighting over the landscape, when we are quarrelling over the legend.

5. Where to begin?

One question remains — and it governs all the rest. To truly reopen this debate, where must we begin? Must we first *disambiguate* the word, patiently agreeing on what it denotes? Or must we, before that, *de-ideologise* it, strip it of its function as a banner? Instinct whispers that we must define first. I doubt it, and deeply: so long as a word remains a rallying cry, no definition will hold — one does not define a banner, one fights over it. Perhaps, then, the true point of entry is not disambiguation but de-ideologisation. To lay down the flag and look, at last, at the object it covered. That is the path the next column will set out to explore.

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